

**BENEFICIARIES PERCEPTION TOWARDS PLACEMENT ASSISTANCE – A STUDY
OF PRADHAN MANTRI KAUSHAL VIKAS YOJANA IN BIJAPUR AND BAGALKOT
DISTRICTS, KARNATAKA**

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Abstract:

The ever changing job market expects updated and upgraded skill sets among the job seekers. A unique skill development program named Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana through its continuous efforts providing the beneficiaries placement opportunities from last few years across the country in various sectors. This paper is focusing on finding the relationship among the beneficiaries perception towards placement assistance with the help of linear regression test. The study was conducted in Bagalkot and Bijapur districts of Karnataka.

A sample of 185 was selected to investigate the beneficiary's opinion, response and expectations. Data from Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana recipients was gathered using a standardized questionnaire. The study established the existence of a favorable perception towards PMKVY's placement cells in terms of their placement services, response to pre-placement training, and fulfilling the job expectations of beneficiaries.

Key Words: Placement, PMKVY, skills, Employment, Beneficiaries, Training, PMKVY.

Introduction:

Unemployment is the Curse for any developing and underdeveloped country in the world. Country like India, with 138 plus Crore populations has a greater responsibility of providing jobs to the educated, skilled and graduate youth to feed themselves and their families. The economy of the country is stretched to 3 trillion and placed in the fifth position of world leading economies. India is struggling to distribute the wealth equally among the population. Several initiatives and efforts have been made to increase the employment opportunities. At present Government of India and state governments are running several skill development programs to the youth, one among them is Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana scheme launched in 2015 by the Honorable Prime Minister Narendra Modi. It's been 7 years that PMKVY trained several young people of the country. Major objective of this PMKVY is to transform the Youth from unskilled to skilled. After undergoing PMKVY training youth got jobs and some of them started their own businesses. Proper placement assistance is provided by PMKVY to the beneficiaries through campus drive and job Melas.

Literature Review

- 1. Employment of the Skilled: Placement Analysis of PMKVY 2.0 (With Reference to Short Term Training under PMKVY 2.0), 2018 IJCRT | Volume 6, Issue 1 February 2018 | ISSN: 2320-2882 :** This paper focuses on job placements analysis of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 2.0 near the 10 states and one union territory their selected for study the states were categorised as high range States middle range states and Lawrence States based upon the enrollment in the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana father sector wise analysis was done on number of candidates enrolled trained and placed finally the paper concluded that in India the major cause behind unemployment is lack of skills among youth power it is the result of Under utilisation of the human resource potential for the paper argues employment can be generated by the government and then only the value for skills will improve the national Skill Development Mission is objective can be achieved only when the government become capable of harnessing the demographic dividend
- 2. Model Appraisal Approach for Pradhanmantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana: A Perspective Dr. Devendra Prasad Pathak, Dr. Anand Kumar, September 2021| IJIRT | Volume 8 Issue 4 | ISSN: 2349-6002 :** this paper aims to recommend a structure of methodology which can be used in in reviewing the impact of p m k v y in India at two stage this paper will offer a Framework for p m k v y in the first stage the shortfalls of p m k v y and in the second stage the historical data of country will be analysed and based upon that the p m k v y utility will be verified the paper is ended by highlighting on employee Expectations Hai supply elasticity consistent gap in demand and supply I mobility supply stocks and wages inelastic demand cost benefit Analysis of P M K V Y
- 3. A Study of Sector wise analysis of Pradhanmantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana(PMKVY), Ravi kumar kumawat, Vol-7 Issue-6 2021 IJARIE-ISSN(O)-2395-4396 :** the major goals of this paper is to analyse the pmkv y wise sector skill Council performances using descriptive statistics and T test for testing the significant differences among different sectors and distribution of resources to training programs further the paper discuss with the concept of p m k v y and the components of p m k v y and analysis of sector wise performance and their differences of p m k v y was done the paper tested the hypothesis of difference in sector wise performance by the short term learning and Priya learning programs do the paper looks like a record study but it was done on secondary data analysis lastly the paper made an attempt to reveal the strength of pmkv y why based upon secondary data sources the conclusion was drawn as there is an existence of significant difference among the sector skill Council the glaring observation of the paper is and an equal amount of resource distribution was formed.
- 4. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY): Effectiveness & Opportunities to Improve, Prof Raj Nehru, Electronic copy available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4076810> :** this paper concentrated on understanding the effectiveness of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana program in Haryana and it also tried to suggest the actions for improvement the study was dependent on descriptive Research Design the major objectives of the study was to understand the mechanism of pmkv y why and to develop solutions to overcome from the existing loopholes of the training program the paper was concluded that most of the training under different sector skill where unable to meet the expected outcomes and the learning as training was poor live certification from p m k v y doesn't ensure was the employment most of the potential employers are not giving wastage and

importance to the p m k v y certificates the quality of skill development training is also not satisfactory training and apprenticeship should be aligned properly so as to achieve the prime objective of this ambitious program

5. **Study of the Profile of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 2.0 in India, Dr. Shanta Arakeri V, Satish Sonawane, International Journal of Advance ISSN – 2347-7075 and Applied Research (IJAAR) Impact Factor –7.328, Peer Reviewed Bi-Monthly, Vol.8 No.5 ,May – June 2021** : Paper intend to throw light on detailed profile of Pradhanmantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana in India the study aims to understand the basic functions of p m k v y the major components of p m k v y such as certain training recognition of prior learning special projects Kaushal and Rojgar Mela placement assistance continuous monitoring standardise branding and communication were discussed and described for the paper the paper concludes that Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana making India of country with skilled youth and efficient announcing of employability and generating of employment where the contributions of Pradhanmantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana to ensure the better livelihood for Indian youth pmkvy scheme will help them in all aspects
6. **A Case Study on the Performance of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana in Dimapur District of Nagaland,Dr. Debojit Konwar, International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD), Volume 6 Issue 1, November-December 2021 Available Online: www.ijtsrd.com e-ISSN: 2456 – 6470** : This paper provides an orientation towards finding the role of pmkvy in improving the skills of youth it aims to study the impact of the scheme on unemployed youth and also try to highlight the problems in implementing this came the study had been conducted in Dimapur town of Nagaland state India some of the observations and analysis are the trainees get a trained in one course and get placed in a different sector which is mismatched Lack of jobs availability in all locations Is another problem as pmkvy by concentrate more on school dropouts rather than formal education required youth need to be reviewed outdated curriculum inadequate trainers lack of training infrastructure are the other challenges that p m k v y is still facing which needs to be addressed
7. **Profile characteristics of trainees under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana in agriculture engineering sector ,Ravi Shinde, Shobhana Gupta and Shrishti Bilaiya, The Pharma Innovation Journal 2022; SP-11(8): 980-984** : This paper is to develop characteristics of another p m k v y in agriculture in various characteristics of winning like age education cast occupation annual income social participation in management skills mass media cosmopolitan orientation innovativeness achievement motivation certificate intention and economic motivation where is the weekly lastly the paper concluded that majority of the respondent software survey their youth and they varigal to carry out their dreams into reality they were education of respondents was higher secondary and most of them belongs to other backward classes with an annual income of more than 200000 rupees most of the respondents a medium to high level employability skills the response characteristics were from using in achieving the skillful human resources
8. **Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY): A unique way to skill development,**

Benny C, International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research, Volume 6, Issue 1 (V): January - March, 2019 : This paper focuses on describing the Pradhanmantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana and its composition secondary data analysis been done to explain the background and framework of p m k v y as the pmkvy scheme is freely accessible and anyone can undergo this training this scheme encourages the youth not only to get employment but also group them as entrepreneurs financial rewards and certificate issued by the government are the advantages of this Pradhanmantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana scheme the young men and women of India will definitely get benefited by this training program.

Problem Statement

A country's wealth can be measured not only in terms of money but also in terms of skills, capabilities and talents. India being second largest country with huge population putting its hundred percent to generate the employment to the youth. skill development programs like PMKVY are promising in upgrading the skills and resulting in the employment opportunities. Beneficiaries are the right people who can share their views, opinions and feedback about placement assistance given by PMKVY. To examine the beneficiaries perception towards placement assistance by PMKVY, this problem statement is formulated.

Objectives

1. To know the beneficiaries opinion and feedback about Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana
2. To study the expectations of beneficiaries towards Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana

Need for the study

Reviewing of training programs will help in improving the framework of the same. while searching for the causes for unemployment, one of the major cause is /employment skills. there is a need of monitoring and assessing these skills and skill development programs, so as to increase the efficiency and training productivity. This is having direct impact on placements. there is a need of studying this issue

Limitations of the Study:

1. Beneficiaries of pmkvy from Bijapur and Bagalkot district were selected and the study is restricted to only these two districts.
2. Only few selected sector skill councils of pmkvy were used to get the opinion and feedback from the beneficiaries.

Research Methodology

Research Design: The combination of the Exploratory and Descriptive Research Designs are adopted for this study. Exploratory design will help in understanding the intensity of the Research problem and provides clarity about the Placement issues of PMKVY. Descriptive Research design is used to ascertain the information for the probable questions. Longitudinal study enables to probe the issues in depth and leads to get more clear inferences.

Secondary data sources: Research Articles from leading Journals, NSDC and PMKVY websites,

Primary Data Sources: A Structured questionnaire is administered by the researcher. Target audiences were interviewed face to face using Questionnaire.

Sampling Method: Convince Sampling Method

Sample Size: 185

Sample Elements: All PMKVY training Beneficiaries in Bijapur and Bagalkot Districts

Sample units: PMKVKs in Bijapur and Bagalkot Districts

Sample Extent: Bijapur and Bagalkot Districts only

Data Analysis tools: SPSS

Results and discussions:

1. Independent T-test

Ho: There is no significant difference in opinion about placement services between Male and Female respondents

H1: There is significant difference in opinion about placement services between Male and Female respondents

Group Statistics					
	Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
PS	Male	101	3.8069	0.543	0.05403
	Female	83	3.8524	0.56987	0.06255

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
PS	Equal variances assumed	0.023	0.879	-0.553	182	0.581	-0.04548	0.08226	-0.20779	0.11684
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.55	171.654	0.583	-0.04548	0.08266	-0.20863	0.11767

Analysis

To determine how male and female respondents felt about placement services, a t-test using independent samples was used. The mean score for males ($M = 3.806$, $SD = 0.543$) was lower than that of females ($M = 3.852$, $SD = 0.569$), but there were no statistically significant differences ($t(-0.550) = 171$, $p=0.583$). It was not significant how much the means varied (mean difference = -0.454, 95% CI: -0.208 to 0.117). Ho is therefore supported.

Interpretation

Do not reject the null hypothesis because the p-value is 0.583, which exceeds the significance level (e.g., 0.05). The statistical significance of the difference between the two means is low. The sample offers convincing justification to draw the conclusion that the two population means are equivalent.

2. Independent T-test

Ho: There is no significant difference in opinion about placement services between urban and Rural respondents

H1: There is significant difference in opinion about placement services between Urban and Rural respondents

Group Statistics					
	Area	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
PT	Urban	96	4.1187	0.51469	0.05253
	Rural	88	4.2136	0.41996	0.04477

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
PT	Equal variances assumed	0.461	0.498	-1.363	182	0.175	-0.09489	0.06963	-0.23227	0.04249
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.375	179.636	0.171	-0.09489	0.06902	-0.23108	0.04131

Analysis

In order to determine the opinion on placement services for Urban and Rural, an independent samples - t-test was used. The mean score for urban areas (M = 4.118, SD = 0.514) was lower than rural areas (M = 4.213, SD = 0.4199), but there were no statistically significant differences ($t(-1.375) = 179, p=0.171$). It was not significant how much the means differed (mean difference = -0.094, 95% CI: -2.310 to 0.413). Ho is therefore supported.

Interpretation: Do not reject the null hypothesis because the p-value is greater than the significance level (e.g., 0.05) and is 0.171. The two means' difference is not statistically significant. That the two population means are equal can be inferred from the sample's robust evidence.

3. Independent T-test

Ho: There is no significant difference in opinion about placement services between Married and Unmarried respondents

H1: There is significant difference in opinion about placement services between Married and Unmarried respondents

Group Statistics					
	Maritalstatus	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
PT	Married	24	4.3083	0.48267	0.09852
	Unmarried	160	4.1425	0.46912	0.03709

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
PT	Equal variances assumed	0.14	0.709	1.609	182	0.109	0.16583	0.10307	-0.03753	0.3692
	Equal variances not assumed			1.575	29.893	0.126	0.16583	0.10527	-0.0492	0.38086

Analysis

To determine the opinion of placement services for Married and Unmarried, an independent samples t-test was used. The mean score for married people ($M = 4.3083$, $SD = 0.482$) was higher than that of single people ($M = 4.142$, $SD = 0.469$), but there were no statistically significant differences in the scores ($t(1.575) = 29.82$, $p=0.126$). It was not significant how much the means differed (mean difference = 0.165, 95% CI: -0.049 to 0.380). H_0 is therefore supported.

Interpretation: Do not reject the null hypothesis because the p-value is 0.126 and above the significance level (e.g., 0.05). The two means' difference is not statistically significant. That the two population means are equal can be inferred from the sample's robust evidence.

4. Chi Square Test : H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the response about placement services between Male and Female respondents

H1: There is significant relationship between the response about placement services between Male and Female respondents

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Sex * I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK	184	100.00%	0	0.00%	184	100.00%

Sex * I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK Crosstabulation						
				I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK		
				Yes	No	Total
Sex	Male	Count	81	20	101	
		Expected Count	79.6	21.4	101	
		% within Sex	80.20%	19.80%	100.00%	
	Female	Count	64	19	83	
		Expected Count	65.4	17.6	83	
		% within Sex	77.10%	22.90%	100.00%	
Total		Count	145	39	184	
		Expected Count	145	39	184	
		% within Sex	78.80%	21.20%	100.00%	

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.260 ^a	1	0.61		
Continuity Correction ^b	0.108	1	0.742		
Likelihood Ratio	0.26	1	0.61		
Fisher's Exact Test				0.717	0.37
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.259	1	0.611		
N of Valid Cases ^b	184				
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.59.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table					

Analysis

$\chi^2 (1, N = 184) = 0.260, p=0.610$, indicating that there is no significant association between sex and response about placement services.

Interpretation

Men were more or less likely than women to say they had received a thorough explanation of the placement aid (80.2% to 77.1%). Don't dismiss H_0

5. Chi Square Test

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the response about placement services between Urban and Rural respondents

H_1 : There is significant relationship between the response about placement services between Urban and Rural respondents

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Area * I	184	100.00%	0	0.00%	184	100.00%

Area * I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK Crosstabulation						
				I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK		
				Yes	No	Total
Area	Urban	Count	80	16	96	
		Expected Count	75.7	20.3	96	
		% within Area	83.30%	16.70%	100.00%	
	Rural	Count	65	23	88	
		Expected Count	69.3	18.7	88	
		% within Area	73.90%	26.10%	100.00%	
Total		Count	145	39	184	
		Expected Count	145	39	184	
		% within Area	78.80%	21.20%	100.00%	

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.465 ^a	1	0.116		
Continuity Correction ^b	1.931	1	0.165		
Likelihood Ratio	2.47	1	0.116		
Fisher's Exact Test				0.149	0.082
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.452	1	0.117		
N of Valid Cases ^b	184				
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 18.65.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table					

Analysis

Urban and rural responses to placement services do not significantly differ from each other ($\chi^2(1, N = 184) = 2.465, p=0.116$).

Interpretation

Urban respondents were more likely than Rural respondents (83.3% to 73.9%) to say that they were fully informed about the placement services. Don't reject the null hypothesis.

6. Chi Square Test

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the response about placement services between Married and unmarried respondents

H1: There is significant relationship between the response about placement services between Married and unmarried respondents

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Maritalstatus * I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK	184	100.00%	0	0.00%	184	100.00%

Maritalstatus * I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK Crosstabulation					
			I was thoroughly informed about the placement assistance offered by the PMKVK		Total
			Yes	No	
Maritalstatus	Married	Count	21	3	24
		Expected Count	18.9	5.1	24
		% within Maritalstatus	87.50%	12.50%	100.00%
	Single	Count	124	36	160
		Expected Count	126.1	33.9	160
		% within Maritalstatus	77.50%	22.50%	100.00%
Total		Count	145	39	184
		Expected Count	145	39	184
		% within Maritalstatus	78.80%	21.20%	100.00%

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.249 ^a	1	0.264		
Continuity Correction ^b	0.722	1	0.395		
Likelihood Ratio	1.388	1	0.239		
Fisher's Exact Test				0.421	0.201
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.243	1	0.265		
N of Valid Cases ^b	184				
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.09.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table					

Analysis

In terms of responses to placement services, there is no statistically significant difference between married and single respondents ($\chi^2(1, N = 184) = 1.249, p = .264$).

Interpretation

Married respondents were more likely than unmarried respondents (87.50% to 77.50%) to say they were fully informed about the placement aid. Please accept H_0

7. Regression Analysis

H_1 : There is a significant impact of placement services offered on Respondents perception towards placement

The hypothesis tests if placement services offered as significant impact on Respondents perception towards placement, the dependent variable Respondents perception towards placement was regressed on predicting variable placement services offered to test the hypothesis H_1 , placement services offered significantly predicted Respondents perception towards placement, $F(1,182), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the placement services in shaping Respondents perception towards placement ($b = 0.295, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of placement services offered, moreover the $R^2 = 0.049$ depicts that the model explains 4% of the variance in Respondents perception towards placement.

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	PSO PTP	0.295	0.049	9.317		0.003	yes

8. Regression Analysis

H1: There is a significant impact of pre placement training on Respondents perception towards placement

The hypothesis tests if pre placement training as significant impact on Respondents perception towards placement, the dependent variable pre placement training was regressed on predicting variable pre placement training offered to test the hypothesis H1, pre placement training significantly predicted Respondents perception towards placement, $F(1,182), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the pre placement training in shaping Respondents perception towards placement ($b=0.542, p < 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of pre placement training, moreover the $R^2 = 0.120$ depicts that the model explains 12% of the variance in Respondents perception towards placement.

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	PPT PTP	0.542	0.12	24.782		0	yes

9.

10. Regression Analysis

H1: There is a significant impact of Beneficiaries Job Expectations on Respondents perception towards placement

The hypothesis tests if Beneficiaries Job Expectations as significant impact on Respondents perception towards placement, the dependent variable Beneficiaries Job Expectations was regressed on predicting variable Beneficiaries Job Expectations to test the hypothesis H1, Beneficiaries Job Expectations significantly predicted Respondents perception towards placement, $F(1,182), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Beneficiaries Job Expectations in shaping Respondents perception towards placement ($b=0.524, p < 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of

pre placement training, moreover the $R^2 = 0.104$ depicts that the model explains 10% of the variance in Respondents perception towards placement.

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R^2	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	BJE PTP	0.524	0.104	21.16		0	Yes

Conclusion:

The study can be concluded that Beneficiaries opinion about placement services, response about pre placement training and expectations about the job will have an impact on perception towards Placement assistance by PMKVK. The study is carried out at PMKVKs in Bagalkot and Bijapur Districts of Karnataka. The study outcomes were stressing upon opinion, response and expectations of the beneficiaries towards the placement assistance.

The beneficiary's opinion about the placement services is satisfactory and the placement cells performing the duties of career guidance, thorough knowledge and experience in recruitment process are their strengths. The study provided sufficient evidences for the statement that there are no significant differences about the opinions, expectations and responses among the genders, areas and marital status about the placement services and preplacement trainings offered by PMKVKs in Bagalkot and Bijapur districts of Karnataka.

Thus the placement assistance provided by the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Kendras in Bagalkot and Bijapur districts of Karnataka is meeting the expectations of the beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana.

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